

Deliverable 5.2

Preliminary report of raising awareness activities, including findings and guidelines for holding similar activities

Contact us

info@biasproject.eu

www.biasproject.eu

LOBA[®]

CrowdHelix

farplas

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Table of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CBR	Case-Based Reasoning
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication
WP	Work Package

Main Author(s)**Name**

Hamza Çınar

Organisation

CHX

Contributors**Name**

Maria Giovanna Zamburlini

Organisation

SVEN

Joana Martinheira

LOBA

Peer Reviews**Name**

Maria Sangiuliano

Organisation

SVEN

Joana Martinheira

LOBA

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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable (D5.2) offers a detailed account of the Raising Awareness Activities conducted within the BIAS project under Task 5.5., with an emphasis on creating and distributing awareness-raising materials and organizing webinars. The main aims of this deliverable are to provide a preliminary report on the activities carried out until M30, describe the methodology employed for content development and underscore the contributions of project partners in carrying out these activities.

The BIAS project seeks to address gender and intersectional biases in AI by implementing educational and awareness initiatives aimed at a diverse array of stakeholders, such as educators, citizen advocacy organizations, and industry professionals. To further this initiative, WP5 has concentrated on two key activities aimed at raising awareness: producing and circulating mini-videos and arranging a series of three online webinars. The aim of these activities is to improve comprehension of the nature of bias, the ways in which it appears in AI systems, and methods for reducing it. Ultimately, this has the objective to create a more favourable environment for the dissemination and exploitation of the project's research and technological development process and results.

The WP5 leader SVEN has been supervising the implementation of the awareness-raising activities, making sure that the content aligns with the project's goals. It is also part of this role to work in close cooperation with other partners to create and provide materials that are based on the most recent research into fairness in AI. The leader of WP5 has played a key role in organizing and facilitating the webinars, working with experts and project partners to ensure that each session addresses the needs of the target audience. The partners' contributions have played a crucial role in successfully implementing the activities documented in this deliverable. As the WP7 leader, LOBA was instrumental in creating the mini-videos, collaborating with BFH (the WP3 leader), NTNU, and ULEID, to guarantee that the content was scientifically valid and appropriate for the target audiences. Webinars were organized through a joint effort that included the WP5 leader, SVEN, and other partners who contributed their expertise, logistical assistance, and content creation for each session. In addition, partnerships with other projects funded by the EU, like DIVERSIFAIR, enhanced the discussions and expanded the webinars' scope.

This deliverable offers a detailed description of the activities completed to date and insights into the planned activities for the rest of the project. It contains details about the scripts for the videos, the organization of the webinars, and the general approach taken to involve and instruct stakeholders on gender and intersectional biases in AI, findings and guidelines for holding similar activities

2. Introduction

Deliverable D5.2 offers a preliminary overview of the awareness-raising activities conducted under Task 5.5 of the BIAS project, which seeks to enhance public comprehension of gender and intersectional biases in Artificial Intelligence (AI). These activities encompass creating and sharing mini-videos and organizing online sessions aimed at raising awareness among stakeholders like educators, advocacy groups, and professionals working with AI. This deliverable is structured as follows:

Section 3 – Methodology details the collaborative method used to create awareness-raising materials and carry out dissemination strategies. A description of the content development process, outreach activities, and the tools and platforms used to promote the project's outputs is included. Task 5.5's methodology was centred around promotion and outreach, which bolstered visibility and engagement. To guarantee that all outputs reached their target audiences effectively, communication activities were incorporated into the awareness-raising process from the outset of planning. Major dissemination strategies encompassed utilizing social media campaigns on LinkedIn and Crowdfunder platform to disseminate the videos and webinars with tailored messages and visuals. Using consortium mailing lists and networks for email marketing, guaranteeing that stakeholder groups like educators, civil society organizations, and AI professionals were notified about forthcoming sessions and video launches; working together with the AI Fairness Cluster, which encompasses cross-promotion of initiatives addressing comparable subjects to enhance visibility and foster a cohesive communication strategy; inclusion in BIAS newsletters, which feature event announcements, video releases, and highlights from events. The newsletters were disseminated widely among the project's network and made available on the BIAS website.

Section 4 – Awareness-Raising Videos. Each video is examined in detail, with an emphasis on its narrative content, promotional activities, and analytics that reflect audience engagement.

Section 5 – Awareness-Raising Sessions outlines the webinars organized so far. The section details the objectives, audience interaction tactics, publicity and distribution efforts, and participant responses for each session.

Section 6 – Future Activities and Conclusions, along with lessons learned so far. It contemplates the achievements and difficulties faced, proposing enhancements for future awareness initiatives, both related to and outside of the project.

Conclusions – The concluding section encapsulates essential insights, lessons acquired, and suggestions for improving future awareness initiatives both within the BIAS project and in broader contexts. The deliverable offers a thorough overview of the awareness-raising efforts, spanning from conceptualization to implementation and impact assessment, by adhering to this structured approach.

3. Methodology

To ensure the accuracy, accessibility, and broad dissemination of content, awareness-raising activities under Task 5.5 were developed through a collaborative and research-driven approach. The methodology consisted of two main components:

- **Development of Awareness Materials** – Producing mini-videos and webinars grounded in research findings. The awareness-raising activities under Task 5.5 were developed through a collaborative approach engaging partners from the consortium to guarantee that the content was rooted in research and spread efficiently.
- **Audience Engagement & Dissemination** – Making certain of extensive involvement and distribution; Audience engagement and dissemination were critical to ensuring broad visibility and impact for the awareness-raising activities under Task 5.5. A targeted outreach strategy was implemented to reach educators, civil society actors, and AI professionals. Communication efforts included regular promotion through the BIAS project's social media channels (Facebook, LinkedIn, X, and Instagram), email campaigns distributed via consortium networks, and featured content in project newsletters. Activities were also published on key platforms such as the AI-on-Demand platform and the Trustworthy AI Helix, a virtual community plays a vital role in ensuring the effective dissemination and exploitation of BIAS project results. By building a strong and self-sustaining community of like-minded stakeholders, we increase the project's impact and ensure its future sustainability (<https://www.biasproject.eu/trustworthy-ai-helix>). Additional visibility was gained through cross-project collaboration with initiatives like the AI Fairness Cluster, helping extend the reach of BIAS outputs. Following each activity, post-event communication included uploading recordings to YouTube, sharing summaries on the website, and promoting content through recap posts and newsletters. These efforts ensured continuous engagement throughout the project lifecycle and helped sustain attention to the topic of gender and intersectional biases in AI.

3.1. Development of Awareness Materials

3.1.1. Mini-Videos

Mini-videos aimed to tackle gender and intersectional biases in AI, drawing on findings from the BIAS project's research. The development process involved these key steps:

Collaborative Design: LOBA (WP7 leader) and BFH (WP3 leader) collaborated closely with the project team to establish key messages, narratives, and visual elements for the mini-videos. They were designed to be accessible, engaging, and informative for a wide audience, including citizen advocacy organizations and educators.

Development of Scripts: To guarantee that the scripts for the mini-videos correspond with research outcomes and are understandable to audiences without specialized knowledge, several members of the consortium reviewed them.

The mini-videos were circulated through the project's communication channels (WP7) and promoted on social media, in newsletters, and within stakeholder networks to ensure visibility among advocacy groups and educators as the webinars aimed at raising awareness were promoted to pertinent communities via project partners, mailing lists, and professional networks, ensuring wide participation.

3.1.2. Webinars

The online awareness-raising sessions were organized featuring content that was intended to be both engaging and accessible. SVEN backed the arrangement of these webinars, in cooperation with Crowdhelix and similar initiatives to the BIAS Project guaranteeing the incorporation of varied viewpoints and interactive features were included. Two of the three webinars implemented (M12, M24, and M36) were promoted via consortium partner networks, social media platforms, and direct engagement with stakeholders.

There was a robust turnout, featuring attendees from diverse sectors such as academia, industry, and civil society. Post-event questionnaires were used to gather feedback, facilitating continuous enhancements in both content and delivery. The BIAS project successfully connected research with practical awareness-building efforts by utilizing the knowledge of consortium partners and incorporating research findings into outreach materials.

4. Awareness-raising videos

Objectives

To capture public attention and foster awareness around the issues and topics addressed in the BIAS project, a **series of three awareness-raising videos** was planned. These videos serve as valuable resources for citizen advocacy organizations and educators, providing them with accessible, educational, and engaging materials. Beyond helping them better understand the work being carried out in BIAS, these videos are also intended as practical tools for teaching and dissemination.

Target audiences

However, this multimedia material is also made for the general public. Awareness-raising videos play a crucial role in engaging the community, making complex and technical content more approachable, and encouraging meaningful discussions. By presenting key concepts in an engaging and visually compelling format, these videos help bridge the gap between research and public understanding, ensuring that critical topics related to bias are accessible to a broad audience.

Each video in the series focuses on a distinct theme:

- **"What is Bias"** – Released in Month 19 (M19), this video explores different forms of bias and their impact on hiring and AI, using a job interview scenario to illustrate how societal stereotypes influence decisions and how biases in data can reinforce discrimination.
- **"How is Bias Experienced"** – Released in Month 26 (M26), this video explores various biases in hiring—such as prestige, age, and gender bias—demonstrating how both human recruiters and AI systems can perpetuate discrimination while introducing Case-Based Reasoning (CBR) and fairness metrics as solutions to promote fairer hiring practices.
- **"How to Recognise Bias"** – Set for release in Month 33 (M33), the final video will focus on identifying bias in different contexts, helping viewers develop critical awareness and recognize the subtle ways bias can manifest.

The first two videos are already available on the BIAS YouTube channel, in the playlist "[Awareness videos](#)", and on the [BIAS website](#), under "Video Gallery".

4.1. First video: What is Bias?

The [first video](#) of the awareness-raising series, released on M19 (May 2024), examines different forms of bias and their impact on society, particularly in hiring decisions and artificial intelligence. "What is Bias" follows the journey of the main character as he makes his way to a job interview. Along the way, labels representing various biases—such as gender, age, race, or educational background—follow the character wherever he goes. These labels are visualised as circles, each symbolising a different bias or stereotype that society assigns to the character. As the character enters the job interview, these labels continue to follow him, highlighting how biases influence perceptions and decisions in real-world situations like hiring. The video aims to show how bias is not only an abstract concept but something that impacts individuals in their everyday experiences. It also explains how word embeddings capture both useful relationships between words and existing social stereotypes. The video illustrates how biases in datasets can reinforce discrimination, especially when multiple personal traits, such as gender and age, intersect. It highlights the

challenges of mitigating bias in technology and the importance of addressing these issues to create fairer systems.

The script was a collaborative effort between BFH, ULEIDEN, and NTNU, who contributed the technical content. LOBA then revised the text, refining the language to make it more engaging, accessible, and suited for a video format. Once the script was finalized, LOBA proceeded with the storyboarding process. In this stage, the goal was to visually reflect the BIAS project's identity, incorporating key design elements that enhance the message.

Shapes were used creatively—such as circles following the main character, symbolizing the labels assigned to individuals due to biases, prejudices, and stereotypes. Colour was also a crucial component, with each circle representing a different type of label. To ensure diversity and inclusivity, the video blends live-action footage of real people from various backgrounds, ages, ethnicities, races, genders, and physical conditions with visual elements that support the information provided by the voice-over.

The voice-over was recorded after the script was finalized, and subtitles were added to enhance comprehension and accessibility, making the video more inclusive for a wider audience. Once the storyboard was completed and approved by the previously mentioned partners, LOBA transitioned from design to animation, bringing the video to life.

It then underwent a validation round by the consortium, and after some adjustments, the final version was officially released in May 2024.

Promotion and Outreach:

The video was published on the BIAS YouTube channel, where it achieved the following results:

- 694 views
- Average view duration: 0:46
- Impressions: 4.4k
- How viewers find this video: mainly through YouTube search (66,3%)

Results and Impact

Over 10 months, the video gathered 694 views, indicating a moderate level of engagement within the project's audience. However, the average view duration of 46 seconds suggests that many viewers did not watch the entire video, possibly dropping off early. This could indicate that the content might need a more engaging hook at the beginning or a more dynamic pacing to retain attention, notes that we have pointed out for the following videos.

With 4.4k impressions, the video had decent visibility, but the conversion rate from impressions to views suggests room for improvement in making the thumbnail and title more compelling to encourage clicks. The fact that 66.3% of viewers found the video through YouTube search is a positive sign, as it shows that the content aligns well with relevant search queries. This suggests that the video's keywords and metadata are effective.

The video was also promoted on the BIAS social media channels (Facebook, LinkedIn, X, and Instagram), [newsletter #3](#), and the [BIAS website](#).

Figure 1: Frame of the "What is Bias" video

4.2. Second Video: How is Bias Experienced?

The [second video](#) of the awareness-raising series, "How is Bias Experienced", released on M26 (December 2024), examines how bias affects hiring decisions, from favouring prestigious degrees over skills to discrimination based on age, gender, and ethnicity. It highlights how AI can perpetuate these biases and introduces Case-Based Reasoning (CBR) as a more transparent hiring method.

By comparing candidates based on skills and experience rather than biased factors, and incorporating fairness metrics, CBR helps ensure more equitable recruitment. The video emphasizes the importance of addressing bias in both human and AI-driven hiring processes to create fairer opportunities for all.

The script was once more a collaborative effort between BFH, ULEIDEN, and NTNU, who contributed the technical content. LOBA then revised the text, refining the language to make it more engaging, accessible, and suited for a video format. Once the script was finalized, LOBA proceeded with the storyboarding process.

This storyboard once again draws from the visual identity of BIAS, using its colours, elements, and shapes to create a dynamic and easily understandable narrative. Once again, the backdrop of the video is set in a recruitment work context, beginning with a line of candidates who are gradually eliminated (indicated by the blurred effect on their faces) due to characteristics and biases associated with them (represented by colourful elements with question marks).

The video then moves to very concrete examples, where two candidate profiles are compared to explain the prioritization sometimes given to candidates from prestigious universities over their experience and skills. The focus then shifts to identity-related biases, with a frame highlighting an older woman and the prejudices recruiters may associate with her. The same exercise is performed with the individuals at the back of the video, followed by a focus on gender biases, specifically related to pregnancy. A young woman appears at

the centre of the frame, surrounded by all the stereotypes she faces simply because of her gender. After this, the video moves to a more technical dimension, explaining how these biases can also be present in AI systems. It presents examples of how these biases can occur, favouring some candidates over others. However, a pause is introduced to challenge this bad practice, and the video rewinds to explain the fair and transparent techniques that these systems should rely on. The video then shifts to a practical explanation of CBR, using the concept of "profile match" to clarify this technique. Using BIAS's colours and shapes, it explains how CBR should be complemented with the application of fairness metrics. The video ends with the same characters from the beginning, now in a more positive and fairer scenario, after the methods and metrics mentioned earlier have been applied.

The voice-over was recorded after the script was finalized, and subtitles were added to enhance comprehension and accessibility, making the video more inclusive for a wider audience.

Once the storyboard was completed and approved by the previously mentioned partners, LOBA transitioned from design to animation, bringing the video to life. It then underwent a validation round by the consortium, and after some adjustments, the final version was officially released in December 2024.

Promotion and Outreach

The video was published on the BIAS YouTube channel, where it achieved the following results:

- 3.866 views
- Average view duration: 2:10
- Impressions: 284
- How viewers find this video: mainly through YouTube advertising (98,4%)
- Audience: mainly female (54,8%), with more that 65 years old (32,9%) and between 18 to 24 years old (20,3%)

Results and Impact

The video, initially published in December 2024, has not performed as expected in terms of engagement and reach, which is not surprising given the timing of its release. December is a month marked by holidays, heavy commercial advertising, and reduced online engagement, which likely limited its organic visibility. Therefore, it was created a paid campaign by mid-March to increase the video's reach and make sure that it would reach more viewers.

Since then, the video's performance has significantly improved, now reaching 3,866 views, largely driven by the ongoing paid campaign, which accounts for 98.4% of traffic.

While impressions remain low at 284, the increase in views suggests the campaign is effectively boosting visibility. A key positive outcome is the rise in average view duration to 2:10, indicating that once viewers click, they stay engaged. This suggests that the content resonates well with the audience, making it a strong foundation for further optimization.

Demographically, the audience remains predominantly female (54.8%), with the largest age group being more than 65 years old (32.9%) and 18-24 years old (20.3%). The campaign's

targeting parameters were refined to make sure the video reached a more diverse audience, with a focus on educators and citizen advocacy professionals.

Overall, the paid campaign, already finalised, has successfully driven views and engagement.

The video is being promoted on the BIAS social media channels (Facebook, LinkedIn, X, and Instagram), and the [BIAS website](#), and it will be communicated in newsletter #4, to be released in June 2025.

Figure 2: Frame of the "How is Bias Experienced" video

Figure 3: Frame of the "How is Bias Experienced" video

5. Awareness-raising sessions

This section details the online awareness-raising sessions that were organised as part of the BIAS project's efforts to promote a better understanding of gender and intersectional bias in AI. The sessions were accessible to everyone and targeted professionals, researchers, students, and policymakers who have an interest in equitable, inclusive, and accountable AI development.

General objectives and target audience:

The awareness-raising sessions form a core part of the BIAS project's strategy to engage stakeholders on the topic of gender and intersectional biases in AI. These sessions are delivered as online webinars and are scheduled across three milestones: M12 (completed), M24 (completed), and M36 (upcoming). Each session is designed to share research-based content in an accessible and interactive format.

The webinar series aimed to raise awareness about how gender and intersectional bias can manifest in AI systems and to explore legal frameworks, tools, and educational approaches that promote fairness. The sessions are designed for a broad audience, including AI developers, legal experts, researchers, policymakers, and students, with the goal of equipping them with practical insights and resources to address bias in their respective fields.

The inaugural webinar, titled "Citizen Science and Artificial Intelligence Technologies" (on 9 October 2023), addressed the legal aspects of fairness in AI and presented practical tools and educational materials created as part of the BIAS project.

Professionals with legal, technical, and academic expertise shared their insights on anti-discrimination law, tools for detecting bias, and inclusive design. Engagement with more than 120 participants was enhanced by interactive features like live Q&A and polls. Through partner networks, social media, and newsletters, the session was promoted, and feedback after the event confirmed that attendees from various sectors had heightened awareness and relevance.

The second webinar, "Intersectional Fairness in AI: Legal Frameworks, Tools, and Learning Opportunities", which took place on 10 December 2024 (M24), was co-organised with the DIVERSIFAIR project to enhance outreach and incorporate a variety of perspectives on fairness in AI. By incorporating a wider variety of expert perspectives from both projects, this joint session broadened the audience and enhanced the content. Engagement was sustained through interactive features, and joint promotion via the dissemination channels of both projects enhanced attendance and visibility. Participants emphasized that cross-project collaboration enhances the understanding of intersectional fairness.

5.1. First webinar - Citizen Science and Artificial Intelligence Technologies

The [first awareness-raising webinar](#) conducted in M12 (9.10.2023), was the foundational session of a series aimed at increasing awareness of gender and intersectional biases in AI. This webinar was designed specifically to familiarize participants with the basic ideas of AI bias, concentrating particularly on gender and intersectionality. The initiative aimed mainly at making people conscious of the possibility of unintentional bias in AI systems, its potential for harm, and how crucial it is to address such biases from the earliest phases of AI technology design and development.

The session sought to provide participants with a clear grasp of the issue and inspire them to participate in further discussion and action.

Promotion and Outreach:

In order to optimize participation and visibility, a thorough promotional strategy was put into action, utilizing various channels and networks of stakeholders. These endeavours encompassed:

- Event images crafted to enhance visual interaction, disseminated through the Trustworthy AI Helix on Crowdhelix Platform and social media (mainly LinkedIn).

Figure 4: First webinar dissemination poster

- Email marketing copy shared through consortium and partner networks to improve outreach.
- Publish on the Trustworthy AI Helix, making sure to involve pertinent stakeholders (<https://www.biasproject.eu/trustworthy-ai-helix/>)
- Dissemination via the AI Fairness Cluster, expanding outreach among professionals in AI fairness (<https://aifairnesscluster.eu/>).

Post-Webinar Communication: A strategic communication plan was implemented after the event to extend the impact of the webinar beyond the live session. Editing the recording of the webinar and uploading it to YouTube to make it accessible for those who were unable to attend live. You can find the recording here on [YouTube](#).

The webinar was featured in the Newsletter #2, which offered an overview of the session, included a link to the recording, and underscored key messages. Endorsing the recap post and recording on social media to attract a broader audience and foster continued conversations.

These joint actions guaranteed extensive visibility and engagement, thereby bolstering the effect of the awareness-raising initiative. The event was posted on the project newsletter as well following the event. (https://www.biasproject.eu/newsletter_bias/newsletter-issue-2/).

Figure 5: Second newsletter "Front page and following pages"

Content Description

The webinar kicked off with a summary of artificial intelligence, detailing the development of AI systems, the influence of data on AI behaviours, and the possibility that these systems could reinforce societal biases. Gender and intersectional biases were given special focus, as they can have a disproportionate impact on marginalized groups and worsen inequalities in fields like hiring practices, facial recognition, and criminal justice systems.

- **AI and Bias:** The session explored how algorithms can reflect and amplify existing societal biases, leading to discriminatory outcomes.
- **The Role of Intersectionality:** A significant part of the discussion focused on intersectionality, emphasizing how gender, race, and other social categories intersect to influence how individuals experience bias. Intersectional bias in AI was framed as a crucial issue that requires tailored solutions to ensure fairness across multiple demographic groups.
- **Ethical Implications:** The webinar also delved into the ethical dilemmas associated with biased AI systems. The discussion covered the responsibility of AI developers, researchers, and organizations in mitigating these biases, emphasizing the need for transparency, accountability, and fairness in AI development.

The webinar showcased expert presentations that offered valuable insights into the complexities of AI bias and its societal effects.

The speakers provided both a theoretical framework and practical advice on how AI developers and organizations can start to identify and reduce bias during the design phase. Additionally, they talked about how policy frameworks and regulations can encourage fairness in AI systems. Furthermore, a case study of a biased AI system was provided, detailing the measures implemented to recognize and rectify the bias. This concrete instance aided participants in grasping the practical difficulties and remedies associated with bias mitigation.

Figure 6: First webinar screenshot

Engagement and Interactivity

To promote involvement and guarantee that the session was participatory, the webinar incorporated several elements aimed at motivating audience engagement:

- **Live Polling:** Throughout the session, participants were invited to take part in live polls, offering insight into their perspectives on AI bias and its ethical implications. This enabled the speakers to customize the conversation according to the audience's viewpoints.
- **Q&A Session:** Following the presentations, a dedicated Q&A segment allowed participants to pose questions directly to the experts.
- **Feedback Questionnaire:** After the webinar, participants were requested to complete a feedback questionnaire aimed at assessing the session's effectiveness and collecting suggestions for future webinars. This input was useful for evaluating the session's impact and fine-tuning upcoming webinars.

Results and Impact

The initial webinar established a strong basis for upcoming sessions, guaranteeing that attendees departed with enhanced insights into AI bias and its ethical ramifications, in addition to pragmatic approaches for tackling these concerns. It represented a vital move in the BIAS project's continuous attempts to increase awareness, encourage cooperation, and advocate action regarding gender and intersectional biases in AI. The first BIAS project webinar attracted a significant number of registrants, culminating in **185 participants**. The distribution of attendees by sector is as follows:

- Civil Society: 9 individuals
- General Public: 11 individuals
- Industry: 26 individuals
- Media: 1 individual
- Policy-makers: 4 individuals
- Scientific Community: 109 individuals

- Other: 25 individuals

The scientific community constituted the largest group of attendees, representing nearly 60% of total registrations and reflecting a robust involvement from individuals focused on research. While industry and civil society made significant contributions, media and policy-makers were less represented. The wide range of attendees underscores the general interest in the subjects addressed during the webinar, stressing the event's significance across multiple sectors.

Webinar participant survey feedback:

The webinar survey feedback highlights a generally positive reception, with most participants satisfied with the content, relevance, and speaker expertise. The platform usability and use of gender-sensitive language were particularly well-rated. However, areas for improvement include increasing interactivity, providing more practical examples, and allowing more time for discussions. Some respondents also suggested offering certificates of attendance and deeper exploration of AI applications in HR. The survey used a Likert scale to measure participants' satisfaction levels. The response options included:

- Yes, very much (Indicating high satisfaction)
- Yes (Indicating general satisfaction)
- Rather not (Indicating slight dissatisfaction)
- Not at all (Indicating strong dissatisfaction)

This scale was applied to various aspects of the webinar, such as content quality, interactivity, platform usability, speaker performance, and methodological approaches. The answers from the participants for each question are given in the “Annex 7.3”.

5.2. Second webinar - Intersectional Fairness in AI: Legal Frameworks, Tools, and Learning Opportunities

The [second awareness-raising webinar](#), held in M24 (10.12.2024), the second awareness-raising webinar was a crucial extension of the BIAS project's initiatives to address gender and intersectional biases in AI. The DIVERSIFAIR project (<https://diversifair-project.eu/>), another EU-funded initiative focused on enhancing fairness in AI systems, co-organized this session in collaboration with BIAS. Through collaboration, the two projects sought to generate a larger influence by involving specialists, stakeholders, and the wider AI community in advocating for socially responsible AI. By adopting this collaborative strategy, a variety of viewpoints could be incorporated, thereby enhancing the webinar's content and broadening its audience.

Figure 7: Second webinar dissemination visual

Figure 8: Official Promotion Visual

Content Description

This webinar expanded on the basic concepts presented in the first session and explored the idea of intersectional fairness in AI more thoroughly, equipping participants with a detailed understanding of the ethical, legal, and practical frameworks that can foster fairness in AI systems. It concentrated on applying fairness frameworks and tools, examining the potential of these methods in practical contexts, especially regarding recruitment and decision-making processes in the workplace.

Figure 9: Second webinar screenshot

Key topics covered:

- **Legal frameworks for fair AI:** The webinar commenced with an in-depth examination of the current legal frameworks that direct the creation and implementation of fair AI systems. The dialogue underscored the necessity of ensuring that AI development is in sync with regulatory standards like the EU Artificial Intelligence Act and other pertinent international frameworks. The focus was on the difficulties and possibilities that these regulations pose for developing AI systems that are transparent, fair, and accountable. The session also examined the role of legal compliance in mitigating biases, offering concrete examples of how legal considerations should be embedded in the design and deployment of AI systems.
- **Methods for evaluating AI fairness:** The webinar dedicated a considerable portion of its time to practical tools and methods used to evaluate the fairness of AI systems. Specialists deliberated on algorithmic auditing tools and fairness assessment frameworks that enable developers to identify, quantify, and reduce bias in AI models.
- Particular focus was placed on the use of these tools in areas like recruitment, where AI is being used more and more to determine hiring and promotion decisions. Through the webinar, participants gained insights into how to choose and apply these tools effectively so that AI systems do not continue gender biases.
- **Learning opportunities, best practices, and future trends:** Experts provided the webinar participants with a range of learning opportunities, such as training courses, toolkits, and other resources, to ensure they were prepared for long-term engagement with the issue of fairness in AI. Best practices for creating equitable AI systems were showcased, emphasizing the importance of collaboration across sectors, the involvement of stakeholders, and the significance of ongoing learning. There was also discussion of the importance of keeping abreast of developing technologies and ethical considerations, as well as of emerging trends in the AI field.

Experts urged participants to engage actively in future EU-funded projects and initiatives aimed at promoting fairness in AI.

In the second webinar, experts who worked on the BIAS and DIVERSIFAIR projects made important contributions. The audience benefited from the theoretical insights and practical recommendations of these professionals, who possessed extensive knowledge of AI ethics, legal frameworks, and bias mitigation strategies. The speakers presented real-world case studies that illustrated the practical use of fairness tools and frameworks, including examples from sectors like HR and public services. Their talks centred on tackling AI bias using proactive design, transparency, and ethical accountability.

The DIVERSIFAIR project was crucial to the webinar, showcasing innovative research on fairness and emphasizing the necessity of including diversity in AI systems. The partnership between BIAS and DIVERSIFAIR united diverse areas of expertise, resulting in a comprehensive strategy for tackling bias and fostering equity in AI. By encountering a variety of viewpoints and approaches, participants enhanced their collective comprehension of fairness in AI.

Engagement and results:

The design of the webinar aimed to enhance participant involvement and interactivity. To foster active involvement, several interactive components were included, such as:

Interactive discussions: The webinar encouraged participants to discuss the topics presented, sharing their personal experiences and insights regarding AI bias and fairness. This open dialogue facilitated the sharing of ideas and practical solutions among a varied group of stakeholders, such as industry professionals, researchers, and educators.

Live polls and Q&A: During the webinar, attendees were invited to participate in live polls to assess their opinions on AI fairness and legal frameworks.

The experts analysed this data in real time, enabling them to adjust the session's content according to the audience's interests and concerns. After the presentations, there was a Q&A session that allowed participants to pose questions and interact directly with the experts. This promoted a deeper involvement with the material and nurtured a sense of community among participants.

Resource sharing: The webinar wrapped up with the distribution of useful resources such as guides, toolkits, and online courses focused on AI fairness. Participants were urged to utilize these materials to enhance their comprehension and to apply the tools and best practices covered in the session. To guarantee wider accessibility, these resources were also published on the project's website

- Scientific Publications: <https://www.biasproject.eu/scientific-publications>
- Public Reports: <https://www.biasproject.eu/public-reports/>
- National Labs: <https://www.biasproject.eu/nationallabs/>

The second webinar, organized in partnership with the DIVERSIFAIR project, greatly contributed to furthering the aims of the BIAS project. It equipped participants with the legal, ethical, and practical resources needed to foster fairness and tackle biases in AI. The webinar facilitated important discussions by leveraging expertise from both projects and involving a varied audience, ensuring these conversations will influence future endeavours in the realm of AI fairness.

Figure 10: Second webinar screenshot

Impact

Webinar participant survey feedback:

The second webinar organized within the BIAS project aimed to involve participants in discussions about intersectional fairness in AI, legal frameworks, and associated tools. A survey was shared with participants to assess the event's effectiveness and their satisfaction, gathering their insights on four crucial factors: their overall satisfaction with the event, the webinar's content and relevance, the speakers' quality, and their likelihood of recommending future Crowdhelix events. The aggregated results of the survey are presented in this analysis, which provides insights into the event's strengths and areas for improvement.

The survey consisted of five main questions, focusing on different aspects of the webinar experience. Each question aimed to gather insights on the overall satisfaction, content relevance, speaker performance, likelihood of recommending the event, and any final thoughts or suggestions from participants.

Scale Used: For the first four questions, a Likert scale ranging from 1 to 10 was used to scale the responses. The scale was designed as follows:

- 1: Very dissatisfied or poor (depending on the question)
- 10: Very satisfied or excellent (depending on the question) Respondents were asked to rate their experience.

General contentment regarding the event: Predominantly affirmative responses: The event received a largely positive satisfaction rating, as 80% of participants rated it between 7 and 10. This suggests that the majority of participants were pleased with the quality and experience of the event. **Room for improvement:** Several low scores were recorded,

including one of 3. This score is a significant outlier and indicates that some attendees were not satisfied. **Content and relevance of the webinar:** Great relevance: The webinar's content was mostly well-received, as 85% of responses fell within the 8-10 range. This shows that most participants deemed the content of the webinar relevant and valuable.

Minor discrepancies: Approximately 10-15% of the audience gave the content a lower rating.

Speaker rating: Generally positive speaker feedback: Most attendees rated the speakers highly, with 80% of responses falling within the 8-10 range. This implies that the speakers successfully conveyed the material and connected with the audience.

Slight room for improvement: A few participants rated the speakers with a 6 or 7, suggesting that there may have been opportunities for the speakers to be more engaging.

Likelihood of recommending Crowdhelix events: Strong likelihood to recommend: The majority of respondents expressed that they would probably recommend Crowdhelix events to others, with 80% giving a rating between 8 and 10. This shows that the participants were highly engaged and satisfied with the event. **Few Hesitant Respondents:** Nevertheless, a few responses were as low as 4 and 5.

6. Future Activities

With the BIAS project nearing completion, a number of essential tasks are scheduled to keep up the impetus regarding gender and intersectional biases in AI. Not only will these activities solidify the understanding acquired from earlier actions, but they will also lay the groundwork for forthcoming efforts to foster equity and inclusivity in AI technologies.

6.1. Third webinar

Looking ahead, one of the main activities is the third raising-awareness webinar, set for M36. This activity will add value to the concluding stage of the BIAS project's awareness-raising activities focused on addressing gender and intersectional biases in AI. This upcoming session will explore advanced strategies for reducing biases and examine the future of AI fairness in a complex technological environment, drawing on insights gained from previous webinars and feedback received. The third webinar will offer a chance to synthesize and reflect on the main insights from the first two webinars. The focus will be on assessing the effects of the discussed tools, legal frameworks, and methodologies, as well as their implementation by organizations and stakeholders. This will encompass talks about difficulties encountered and approaches that have proven successful in minimizing bias in AI systems. A key feature of the third webinar will be a discussion of new trends, technological developments, and emerging difficulties connected to fairness in AI.

The third webinar will continue the tradition of cross-collaboration with other EU-funded projects and initiatives. By engaging with projects like DIVERSIFAIR and others such as ENFIELD Project (<https://www.enfield-project.eu/>) working in the AI fairness and ethics space, a possible joint webinar will allow for the exchange of knowledge, resources, and insights across initiatives. This collaborative approach is crucial to building a unified strategy for addressing bias in AI systems across different sectors. Participants can expect the third webinar to furnish them with a thoroughgoing, practical understanding of how to ensure fairness in AI systems, focusing on new technologies and forthcoming difficulties. It will also enable participants to connect with both peers and specialists, thus improving their understanding and readiness to address biases in their own AI applications. Insights gained during this webinar will provide a basis for future research, policy development, and educational initiatives designed to advance fairness in AI systems.

6.2. Awareness-raising videos

The third and final video in the awareness-raising series will be released in July 2025. It will primarily focus on recognizing biases, though its concept will be refined and adapted as needed.

Preparation for the video will begin in April 2025, starting with the script, which will be developed collaboratively by LOBA and BFH. The production process will follow the same steps as the previous videos: storyboard creation, voice-over recording, and video editing and animation.

Once completed, the video will be published on the BIAS YouTube channel (under the "Awareness Videos" playlist) and promoted through the project's social media platforms and newsletter.

This final awareness-raising video will maintain the same visual identity and design elements as the previous ones, ensuring a cohesive and consistent look.

7. Conclusions

This final awareness-raising video will maintain the same visual identity and design elements as the previous ones, ensuring a cohesive and consistent look

The deliverable D5.2 – Awareness Raising Activities outlines the work done in Task 5.5 of the BIAS project to raise awareness of gender and intersectional biases in AI. The project effectively engaged a wide range of stakeholders, such as researchers, industry professionals, policymakers, and advocacy groups, through a strategic mix of mini-videos and interactive webinars.

The chosen methodology ensured that all awareness-raising activities were grounded in evidence and accessible to everyone. The process of developing content, informed by the BIAS project's research findings, was a joint endeavor that involved important consortium partners. The mini-videos offered an engaging and easily comprehensible introduction to AI biases, whereas the webinars enabled detailed discussions and fostered participant interaction and knowledge sharing.

These activities gained enhanced visibility and impact thanks to a well-organized promotion and outreach strategy. The project utilized social media, consortium networks, the AI-on-Demand platform, and partnerships with initiatives such as the AI Fairness Cluster and Trustworthy AI Helix to guarantee widespread dissemination. Communication after the event, which included uploads to YouTube and features in newsletters, further broadened the impact of these initiatives.

The outcomes reveal robust involvement, as evidenced by elevated participation rates in the webinars and favourable responses from participants. The information gathered via post-event evaluations underscores the success of both the content and the methods of delivery, while also providing ideas for additional enhancement.

To conclude, the BIAS project has successfully linked research with public involvement, promoting a wider comprehension of AI fairness issues. As we move ahead, the insights gained from these activities will guide future dissemination initiatives, guaranteeing ongoing advancement toward AI systems that are more inclusive and equitable. After this preliminary report on awareness raising sessions, a final report will be due M46 that will detail all sessions as well as learnings from evaluations and assessments.

8. Annexes

8.1. Webinar agendas

Citizen Science and Artificial Intelligence Technologies: Collaborating for an Innovative and Unbiased Future

online

October 2023

Partners

BIAS

Citizen Science and Artificial Intelligence Technologies: Collaborating for an Innovative and Unbiased

09.10.2023

DESCRIPTION:

“Citizen Science and Artificial Intelligence Technologies” is an online webinar that aims to bring together the power of citizen participation and the potential of emerging technologies.

In this era of rapid technological advancements, citizen science provides a unique opportunity to engage individuals from diverse backgrounds in scientific research and innovation. By involving citizens in data collection, analysis, and problem-solving, we can tap into the collective intelligence of the crowd, accelerating scientific discovery and fostering a deeper understanding of our world.

Interdisciplinarity in these areas unlocks new possibilities for addressing complex challenges in areas like the labour market, environmental conservation, public health, and urban planning. This collaboration enables harnessing the power of technology to amplify the impact of citizen-driven initiatives, facilitating real-time data collection and data sharing. At the same time, practices and methodologies inspired by citizen-science can be used to consult and engage users and stakeholders in AI research, and make sure computer scientists get input and feedback that contribute to increasing inclusiveness and trustworthiness of the systems they design.

This webinar is a combined effort of the TIME4CS and BIAS projects, bringing together the Citizen Science Helix and the Trustworthy AI Helix communities.

TIME (CET)	TITLE	SPEAKER
14.00 - 14.15	Welcome and presentation of the TIME4CS & BIAS projects	TIME4CS - Claudia Iasillo /Alessio Spera - APRE BIAS: Roger Soora - NTNU
14.15 - 14.25	Crowdhelix Platform, Citizen Science and Trustworthy AI Helixes for impact acceleration and future collaboration	Crowdhelix
14.25 - 14.40	AI in Citizen Science projects: examples	TIME4CS: Jacob Sherson - Aarhus University, Center for Hybrid Intelligence
15.05 - 15.20	Citizens' engagement on tackling gender and intersectional biases in AI	BIAS: Carlotta Rigotti & Eduard Villaronga - Leiden University
14.40 - 15.05	Citizen Science tools and AI	TIME4CS: Gitte Kragh, Aarhus University
15.20 - 15.35	Novel tools for bias identification and mitigation in AI systems - The Debiaser	BIAS: Masha Kurpicz-Briki - Bern University of Applied Sciences
15.35 - 15.40	Wrap up and conclusion	

Consortium:

 time4cs@apre.it

 www.time4cs.eu

[@time4cs](https://twitter.com/time4cs)

Intersectional Fairness in AI: Legal Frameworks, Tools, and Learning Opportunities

10 December 2024, 3 PM CET

***Please note that all times are in CET**

15:00 Welcome message

Silvia Ecclesia, PhD Candidate, Norwegian University of Science and Technology

15:05 Introduction to the BIAS project

Roger A. Søråa, Professor in Science & Technology Studies in NTNU Dep. of Interdisciplinary Studies of Culture & Senior Researcher at NTNU Social Research

15:20 DIVERSIFAIR: Building a Fairer Future for AI in Europe

Dr. Lizette Maljaars, Senior Project Manager, TNO ICT, Strategy & Policy

15:35 Roundtable Discussion: Shaping the Future: The Impact of the AI Act on the Workplace

- Carlotta Rigotti, post-doc researcher in law, gender, and technology, eLaw Center for Law and Digital Technologies, Leiden University
- Susan Leavy Assistant Professor at the School of Information and Communication, University College Dublin
- Ilina Georgieva Senior Specialist Scientist in AI Governance and Regulation at TNO/ External PhD Researcher at Leiden University

16:05 AI Auditing and Bias Detection:

Gemma Galdon Clavell, CEO and Founder of ETICAS AI (ES)

16:20 Navigating fair AI use in recruitment: the BIAS Capacity Building programme

Maria Sangiuliano, PhD, Research Director and Programme Manager, Smart Venice srl

16:35 Crowdhelix Platform, Trustworthy AI Helix for Impact Acceleration and Future Collaboration

Cais Jurgens, Head of Membership Development, Crowdhelix

16:45 Wrap up

8.2. Raising Awareness Video Screenshots

native english speaker

+50 years old

male

/resume:

Globe-trotting Indran has lived and worked in 11 countries, and snorkeled in 4 out of 5 continents. With a CPA background and 30 years of experience, Indran thrives in transforming finance functions from "Chaos to Clarity!". His portfolio includes establishing new ventures, raising capital, and restructuring operations across multiple sectors and regions. Indran provides financial stewardship, partnering with operational teams to execute goals.

How is Bias Experienced?

Prestige vs. Experience

Aadhya Bakshi

A promising young talent with a strong academic foundation from University of Oxford, one of the leading institutions in the world. Her youthful energy, combined with her educational background, makes her a highly adaptable and driven individual, ready to contribute and grow within the financial sector.

- University of Oxford
- England

She has studied at top institutions, successfully completing all academic modules and consistently excelling in each one.

Emily Smith

A highly skilled professional with extensive expertise in the financial sector. She demonstrates strong leadership abilities, guiding teams toward achieving strategic goals with efficiency and precision.

- Uni Verbum

Her experience encompasses launching new ventures, securing structure, and optimizing operational processes across diverse industries and business environments.

a candidate's

How is Bias Experienced?

5 years experience

CBR compares

How is Bias Experienced?

Profile Match

5 years experience

french speaker

mba

5 years experience

a clear, easy to understand reason

8.3. Second Webinar – Participant Survey Results

BIAS

Mitigating biases
of AI in the
labour market

Consortium

NTNU

UNIVERSITY
OF ICELAND

LOBA[®]

CrowdHelix

SMARTVENICE

Universiteit
Leiden
eLaw

DigiTouch

farplas

Bern University
of Applied Sciences

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email

info@biasproject.eu

website

www.biasproject.eu

social media

[@BIASProjectEU](https://twitter.com/BIASProjectEU)

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